

REGIONAL VARIATIONS OF ENGLISH IN SOCIAL MEDIA

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Abstract: *English is spoken by over 500 million people. In terms of the number of speakers, it is second only to Chinese and Hindi. The widespread use of the English language and its fame throughout the world is due to the extensive colonization of the British Empire in the 18th and 19th centuries, as well as the political influence and economic dominance of the United States from the late nineteenth century to the present day.*

Key words: *public speakers, grammatical construction, linguists, regional dialects, British accent, linguistic.*

РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ВАРИАНТЫ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В СОЦСЕТЯХ

Аннотация: *На английском языке говорят более 500 миллионов человек. По количеству говорящих он уступает только китайскому и хинди. Широкое использование английского языка и его известность во всем мире связаны с обширной колонизацией Британской империи в 18-м и 19-м веках, а также с политическим влиянием и экономическим господством Соединенных Штатов с конца девятнадцатого века до сегодняшней день.*

Ключевые слова: *ораторы, грамматическая конструкция, лингвисты, региональные диалекты, британский акцент, лингвистический.*

INTRODUCTION

It is not surprising that the speech of public speakers in English and living in different countries (USA, India, Australia and the UK) differs significantly in pronunciation. Speakers also use a variety of words and grammatical structures. Sometimes some dialects of the English language are difficult to understand even for native speakers who absorb the vocabulary and grammar of their region from birth.

Two main dialects. In the UK, most residents speak the "southern British" dialect. Otherwise, this dialect is also called "BBC Language" or "Royal English". With the development of the influence of the United States of America, another dialect became widespread, known as "American English".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In addition, in some countries English has its own peculiarities of pronunciation, the use of certain words, and the grammatical construction of sentences. So, in southern British there are more subdialects: Cockney, Georgie, and in American English there are subdialects: African American English or Canadian English, Boston, Chicago and even Hawaiian.

More than 70% of native English speakers live in America, so the American English dialect is becoming dominant in the modern world. No less niche in the dialects of the English language is occupied by the Australian variant, which is informally called "strain". This dialect is spoken by the main population of Australia and New Zealand. The main native dialects of English are often divided by linguists into three general categories: those of the British Isles (Great Britain) as well as those of North America (USA and Canada) and Australasia (India, Australia and New Zealand). Dialects can be associated not only with a place, but also with certain social groups.

A particular English-speaking country is dominated by a form of the language that is considered the standard English for that country. The standard English languages of different

countries differ from each other, and each of them can be considered a dialect when talking about English in general. Standard English is often associated with the more educated sections of society.

Main differences between dialects of British English:

RESULTS

There are slight differences in formal written English in the UK (for example, the words *wee* and *little*, meaning "small, little", can be interchanged, however, the former is more likely to be read in the writing of a person from Northern England or Northern Ireland (more often Scotland) than in a letter from a person from the southern parts of the country or Wales).

The forms of spoken English, on the contrary, are very different from each other - more than in other English-speaking countries. For this reason, it is quite difficult to apply the concept of "British English" to oral speech.

The term "British English" is also often used as a synonym for "Commonwealth English", which refers to the varieties of English used in the countries of the Commonwealth of Nations (except for countries with their own unique dialect, such as Canada or Australia).

Regional dialects of Great Britain. In addition to the above, linguists also distinguish several regional dialects: northern, central, southwestern, southeastern, Scottish, Welsh and Irish. A complete list of dialects can be found on Wikipedia, we will only give a link to a list of variants of English, which is spoken in England.

The biggest discrepancies among dialects are observed in phonetics. Phonetic variations are sometimes found in almost every word, and it is they who primarily determine one or another variant or dialect of the English language. For example, *love* (Russian *love*) is "lav" among the English, "liv" among the Irish, and "luv" among the Scots; *day* (Russian *day*) as part of the days of the week, the Londoners pronounce it as "day", and the Welsh - "di".

The Irish dialect has a more even, "neutral" pronunciation, replacing "complex" sounds with simpler ones, for example, the interdental in the words *that*, *think* is ordinary. The Irish, in addition, do not save sounds between consonants, they add neutral ones: for example, *film* sounds like "filem". Irish English is more musical, melodious - which comes from Celtic; Australian is characterized by a slower rhythm and a flat intonation scale.

Received Pronunciation (RP) is a variant of the English language with the status of a national standard, which is rooted in the language of the educated population of London and the south-east of England. Its basis is "correct English".

DISCUSSION

It is this variant of the language that the best private schools (Eton, Winchester, Harrow, Rugby) and universities (Oxford, Cambridge) use to educate students and create teaching aids. This is the classical, literary English that is taught, for example, in our foreign language and which is the basis of any English course in linguistic schools for foreigners. The standard pronunciation is often referred to as Royal English or BBC English.

In the United Kingdom itself, the following dialects can be distinguished: Scottish, Northern, Irish, Central, South Eastern, Welsh and South Eastern. The latter, by the way, has acquired a national status, since it is based on "correct English". This dialect is used in the best private schools and universities in the UK such as Rugby, Eton, Harrow, Winchester, Cambridge, Oxford.

The sites listed above will help you learn to distinguish different dialects by ear, but you will only find very short recordings on them. If you want to listen to how a particular dialect sounds in a natural environment, we advise you to watch TV series or films where this dialect is used.

For example, “[Friends](#)” is a great example of a New York accent, and [Nancy Donovan](#) from “30 Rock” has a Boston accent. New York and Boston are not far from each other, but how different is the pronunciation of their inhabitants!

You'll find a list of American accents used in various films on the [TV Tropes](#) website.

Downton [Abbey](#) is a perfect illustration of British accents. After watching it, you will understand that in Britain the main difference in pronunciation is not even due to the area where you were born, but to social status, financial situation and profession.

It is even better to watch some modern series - for example, “[The IT Crowd](#)”. The speech in it is more relevant and realistic, and there are enough different dialects (for example, one of the characters is Irish).

A mixture of different dialects and accents is characteristic of many series. For example, in the great American drama "[Lie To Me](#)" the main character speaks with a British accent, and in the TV series "[Leverage](#)" characters with accents from the American South to Britain are collected.

Keep in mind that some actors are clever at imitating dialects. For example, Gillian Anderson, whom you probably remember from the X-Files series, is American, but in the series “[The Fall](#)” she has a strong British accent. Fake accents are always a little exaggerated and easy to imitate, but if you want to listen to the real dialect, it's best to check [IMDb](#) to see where the actor comes from.

Podcasts and audiobooks. If you're a fan of podcasts and audiobooks, you're sure to find ones that are well-read with the accent you need.

To listen to a pure British accent, select books read by [Stephen Fry](#). A fine example of an American storyteller is Ron McLarty. Listen to him read "[Inherent Vice](#)" by Thomas Pynchon.

Some audiobooks are read by roles. A good example of such a recording is “The [Golden Compass](#)” by Philip Pullman. The text from the author is read by Pullman himself, and the characters are voiced by a professional actor.

CONCLUSIONS

Podcasts are another great way to listen to different dialects. In podcasts, speech is more natural, conversational and spontaneous. For Australian dialects, check out [Oz Podcasts](#). A list of UK podcasts can be found at the [British Podcast Awards](#).

Podcasts cover a wide variety of topics, so you're bound to find ones that interest you. For example, the podcasts on [99% Invisible](#) talk about all sorts of fun and little-known facts. Here [is a podcast about horses](#). There are podcast lists - one from [Complex](#), and another from [Entertainment Weekly](#).

The same literary, classical dialect of the British version is taught in our secondary schools, colleges and universities in foreign language. It is the basis for any English courses in every linguistic school where foreigners are taught the language.

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